

Action of Urea upon Thiosemicarbazides: Simultaneous Formation of Thiol-keto-triazoles, Amino-keto-thio-diazoles, Endoxytriazole and Amino-thiol-triazoles.

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1:4-Disubstituted thiosemicarbazides exist in two isomeric forms and their structure has been a subject of controversy between Busch and Marckwald. Marckwald (*Ber.*, 1892, 25, 3098) and Dixon (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1892, 81, 1012) explain this phenomenon on stereochemical grounds and Busch (*Ber.*, 1901, 34, 320) explains it as being due to structural isomerides of the type $H_2N-NR-CS-NHR$ and $NHR-NH-CS-NHR$. No such isomerism is known to exist among 4-monosubstituted thiosemicarbazides; still it cannot be said that there is no possibility of the *syn-anti* isomerism of Marckwald with them, whilst Busch's position isomerism is out of the question.

The present investigation was undertaken with the object of elucidating the nature of 4-mono-substituted thiosemicarbazides by observing their reaction with carbamide. Four different compounds are simultaneously formed in the reaction and their formation can be explained on the assumption that the thiosemicarbazides react both in the *syn*- and the *anti*-forms. The formation of 1-phenyl-2-keto-5-thiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-triazole from 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide may be explained by assuming the thiosemicarbazide to react in its *anti*-form, thus:

Such keto-thiol-triazoles were prepared by Freund and Schander (*Ber.*, 1896, 29, 2506), Arndt, Milde and Tschenschler (*Ber.*, 1922, 55, 341) and by Fromm and Nehring (*Ber.*, 1923, 56, 1870).

The formation of 2-keto-5-phenylamino-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole necessitates the assumption of the *syn*-form :

Similar keto-amino-thiodiazoles were prepared by Busch (*Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 320, 2328; 1902, **35**, 973; 1904, **37**, 2333; 1909, **42**, 4768; 1911, **44**, 561, 1580) and by Nirdlinger and Acree (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 224).

The compound formed at an intermediate stage during the formation of 2:5-endoxy-1:3:4-triazole may owe its formation to the *anti*-form of the thiosemicarbazide, thus :

When this loses a molecule of sulphuretted hydrogen, the oxygen atom forms a bridge between the 2:5-carbon atoms so as to yield the endoxytriazole :

Though Marckwald, Busch and others prepared derivatives of endoxy-, endothio- and endoimino-triazoles*, the parent endoxytriazole has been prepared for the first time by the present authors.

Besides the three compounds mentioned above there is obtained 1-phenyl-2-phenylamino-5-thiol-1:3:4-triazole, for the formation of which urea is not required: one molecule of the thiosemicarbazide in the *syn*-form reacts with another in the *anti*-form with the

* Schneider, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1890, **67**, 263; Marckwald, *Ber.*, 1892, **25**, 3118; 1896, **29**, 2923; Busch, *loc. cit.*; Nirdlinger and Acree, *loc. cit.*

splitting off of one molecule of sulphuretted hydrogen and one molecule of hydrazine, thus :

These four types of compounds have been obtained also from 4-tolyl- and 4-xyl-yl-thiosemicarbazides.

Urea reacts with thiosemicarbazide to give only two compounds, *vis.*, dihydroketo-thioltriazole and endoxytriazole, thus :

Seeing that the endoxy compound is invariably formed in the above reactions, it was naturally expected that the action of urea upon semicarbazide would yield this substance. In fact, it is formed, in good yield, when urea acts upon semicarbazide, to the exclusion of other compounds. Evidently, the reaction proceeds thus :

EXPERIMENTAL.

Four substances are produced simultaneously in the reaction between urea and a 4-R-thiosemicarbazide. These substances, the isolation of which depends on their respective solubilities are therefore taken in the following order: Type I, readily soluble in water; Type II, soluble in alkaline solution; Type III, soluble in boiling water; Type IV, insoluble in water and in alkaline solution.

Urea and 4-Phenylthiosemicarbazide.—4-Phenylthiosemicarbazide (10 g.) and freshly dried urea (8.5 g.) were thoroughly mixed and heated in an oil-bath at 130-135° during five to six hours. The mass began to melt at 120° and at 130° ammonia and sulphuretted

hydrogen were profusely evolved. After about one hour the reaction mixture assumed a brownish appearance which gradually disappeared as the heating was prolonged. After five hours' heating evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen came to an end, but there was still a slight liberation of ammonia. The reaction mixture was then poured into warm water (200 c.c.) and the pasty mass thus obtained was thoroughly triturated in a mortar; on being allowed to stand for some time in contact with water it solidified. The mixture was then filtered.

1-Phenyl-2-keto-5-thiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-triazole.—(Type I).

Iodine dissolved in potassium iodide solution was added to the aqueous extract in slight excess when a voluminous precipitate was obtained. The precipitate was washed free from iodine with potassium iodide solution, and water, and was then heated under reflux with tin and hydrochloric acid for about an hour when the yellow mass gradually went into solution. It was filtered hot and on cooling gave a white crystalline mass which was crystallised from a large quantity of water, m.p. 197°. Arndt, Milde and Tschenscher (*loc. cit.*) give m.p. 196-197°; yield 0.8 g. It is soluble in alkali, gives insoluble lead and mercury mercaptides, and is oxidised to a yellow disulphide on exposure to the air. (Found: N, 20.32. $C_8H_7ON_3S$, H_2O requires N, 19.91 per cent.).

The Disulphide.—The yellow precipitate obtained by the addition of iodine to the aqueous extract was further purified by crystallisation from dilute alcohol, m.p. 290°. Arndt (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 286°. (Found: N, 21.23. $C_{16}H_{12}O_2N_6S_2$, requires N, 21.98 per cent.).

The Dimethyl Derivative.—The phenyl triazole (0.5 g.) was dissolved in dilute potassium hydroxide solution and shaken vigorously with methyl iodide (2 c.c.) for a few minutes when a white crystalline precipitate separated: it crystallised from water in fine soft needles, m.p. 110°. (Found: N, 18.88. $C_{10}H_{11}ON_3S$ requires N, 19.00 per cent.).

The solid insoluble product was thoroughly triturated in a mortar with normal sodium hydroxide solution when a portion was found to have gone into solution; the mixture was filtered.

1-Phenyl-2-phenylamino-5-thiol-1:3:4-triazole.—(Type II).

The filtrate was neutralised with dilute hydrochloric acid when a white amorphous precipitate was obtained. It was crystallised from

dilute acetone, m.p. 210°; yield 1·8 g. (Found: S, 12·27. $C_{14}H_{14}N_4S$ requires S, 11·94 per cent.). It gives an insoluble disulphide with iodine.

The *methyl derivative* was prepared by shaking the above substance (0·5 g.) in sodium hydroxide solution with methyl iodide (8 c.c.). It was crystallised from dilute alcohol; m.p. 209°. (Found: N, 19·23. $C_{14}H_{14}N_4S$ requires N, 19·86 per cent.).

The *benzyl derivative* was prepared by heating molecular quantities of the thiol compound and benzyl chloride in alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (1 mol.) under reflux for about half an hour. After removing the alcohol, the residue was freed from sodium chloride by washing with boiling water. Finally, it was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 153-154°. Fromm (*Annalen*, 433, 1) gives m.p. 154°.

2:5-Endoxy-1:3:4-triazole.—(Type III).

The insoluble residue was boiled repeatedly with large quantities of water and filtered hot; the filtrate gave a beautiful white crystalline mass which was crystallised from a large quantity of water, m.p. 250°; it is insoluble in alkali and acetone; yield 2 g. (Found: N, 50·82. C_2HON_3 requires N, 50·60 per cent.).

N-Acetyl-endoxytriazole.—The above endoxy compound (1·5 g.) was boiled under reflux with acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) for three hours and the reaction mixture poured into water: a white precipitate was obtained which was crystallised twice from water; m.p. 242°. (Found: N, 33·55. $C_4H_5O_2N_3$ requires N, 33·60 per cent.).

2-Keto-5-phenylamino-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole.—(Type IV)

The residue insoluble in water and aqueous alkali, after crystallisation from dilute acetone, had m.p. 246°; yield 0·5 g. (Found: N, 21·3. $C_8H_9ON_3S$ requires N, 21·76 per cent.).

Urea and p-Tolylthiosemicarbazide.

An intimate mixture of 4-*p*-tolylthiosemicarbazide (9 g.) and freshly dried urea (7·5 g.) was heated in an oil-bath at 130-135° for about six hours when ammonia and sulphuretted hydrogen were profusely evolved. By following the process of extraction gone through in the previous case, an aqueous extract and a solid were obtained.

Isolation of the Disulphide of 1-Tolyl-2-keto-5-thiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-triazole.—(Type I).

The aqueous extract gave with iodine solution a voluminous precipitate which was washed with potassium iodide solution and water and was further purified by precipitation from an alcoholic solution by the addition of water, m.p. 175°; yield 1.3 g. (Found: N, 20.55. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 20.38 per cent.).

Dimethyl derivative.—The disulphide (1 g.) was reduced with tin and hydrochloric acid by heating under reflux for about an hour. The disulphide gradually went into solution and on diluting this, a white precipitate was obtained. The precipitate after being washed several times with water was quickly dissolved in alkali and shaken well with methyl iodide (2.5 c.c.). After some time a white crystalline mass separated which was purified by crystallisation from water, m.p. 142°. (Found: N, 17.92. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_2S$ requires N, 17.87 per cent.).

The solid, left after the product of reaction was digested with water, was treated with alkali when a portion went into solution.

1-Tolyl-2-tolylamino-5-thiol-1:3:4-triazole.—(Type II).

The alkaline solution gave a white amorphous precipitate on acidification with hydrochloric acid, which was crystallised from dilute acetone, m.p. 187°; yield 1.5 g. (Found: S, 10.85. $C_{18}H_{18}N_2S$ requires S, 10.81 per cent.). It gives a yellow disulphide with iodine.

Benzoyl derivative.—The above substance (0.6 g.) was dissolved in alkali and shaken with benzoyl chloride (3.5 c.c.). A faintly yellow precipitate separated; this was collected, washed with dilute alkali and water, and crystallised from acetone, m.p. 100°. (Found: S, 7.86. $C_{23}H_{20}ON_2S$ requires S, 8.0 per cent.).

Methyl derivative.—Methyl iodide (3 c.c.) was added to an alkali solution of the substance (0.6 g.) and the mixture was vigorously shaken when a crystalline precipitate separated: it was crystallised from water, m.p. 178°. (Found: N, 18.04. $C_{17}H_{18}N_2S$ requires N, 18.06 per cent.).

2:5-Endoxy-1:3:4-triazole.—(Type III).

The residue was treated with a large quantity of boiling water; the filtrate gave crystals, m.p. 250°, in every respect identical with the substance obtained from 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide.

2-Keto-5-tolylamino-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole.—(Type IV).

The solid which remained after treatment with boiling water was crystallised from alcohol (90 per cent.), m.p. 227° (Found: N, 20·13. $C_9H_9ON_2S$ requires N, 20·29 per cent.).

Urea and Xylyl-thiosemicarbazide.

A mixture of 4-xylyl-thiosemicarbazide (10 g.) and freshly dried urea (7·5 g.) was heated at 130-140° for about six hours during which ammonia and sulphuretted hydrogen were profusely evolved. The same process as before was followed for separating the four products of this reaction.

1-Xylyl-2-keto-5-thiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-triazole.—(Type I).

As in the case of the phenyl and tolyl compounds, a yellow insoluble disulphide was obtained from the aqueous extract. This was reduced with tin and hydrochloric acid: on dilution with water the solution gave a white crystalline precipitate. It was thoroughly washed with water, crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid and dried in a vacuum desiccator, m.p. 195°; yield 0·6 g. (Found: N, 19·82. $C_{10}H_{11}ON_2S$ requires N, 19·00 per cent.).

The Disulphide.—The crude disulphide obtained by the addition of iodine to the aqueous extract, was purified by dissolving in acetone and precipitating with water, m.p. 240°. (Found: N, 19·17. $C_{20}H_{20}O_2N_4S_2$ requires N, 19·09 per cent.).

The solid, insoluble in water, was treated with dilute alkali when a portion went into solution.

1-Xylyl-2-xylylamino-5-thiol-1:3:4-triazole.—(Type II).

The alkaline extract on acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid gave a white amorphous precipitate which, after crystallisation from acetone, had m.p. 200°, yield 0·8 g. (Found: S, 9·39. $C_{18}H_{18}N_4S$ requires S, 9·87 per cent.).

2:5-Endoxy-1:3:4-triazole.—(Type III).

The residue was boiled several times with large quantities of water. The aqueous solution yielded a substance, m.p. 250° identical with the endoxytriazole already obtained.

2-Keto-5-xylylamino-5-thiol-1:3:4-thiodiazole.—(Type IV).

The insoluble residue was crystallised from dilute acetone, m.p. 218-219°. (Found: N, 18·97. $C_{10}H_{11}ON_2S$ requires N, 19·00 per cent.).

Urea and Thiosemicarbazide.

A mixture of thiosemicarbazide (6 g.) and freshly dried urea (10 g.) was heated for six hours at 125-130° during which ammonia and sulphuretted hydrogen were evolved. The molten mass was then well ground with water in a mortar and the solid residue was found to be insoluble in alkali. It was crystallised from a large quantity of water when it melted at 250°. It was found to be identical with the endoxytriazole already obtained.

Isolation of Keto-thioltriazole Disulphide.

The cold aqueous extract was treated gradually with iodine solution when a yellow precipitate was obtained which dissolved again on shaking. After iodine was added in excess, the solution was evaporated to half its bulk and cooled when a small quantity of a white crystalline precipitate came out, m.p. 246°. As the yield of the disulphide was very poor, the parent substance (thiourea-zole) could not be prepared. Arndt, Milde and Tschenschner (*loc. cit.*) give the m.p. 246° for the disulphide. (Found: N, 36.93. $C_4H_4O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 36.20 per cent.)

Action of Urea upon Semicarbazide.

A mixture of semicarbazide (5 g.) and freshly dried urea (10 g.) was heated at 140° for about six hours. By following the process indicated above, endoxytriazole melting at 250° was obtained; yield 4 g. Neither the aqueous nor the alkaline extract gave any other compound. Evidently, the reaction proceeds in this case only in one direction.

The action of thiourea upon semicarbazides and thiosemicarbazides is being studied and will form the subject of a subsequent communication.

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